

A Study of Socio-Economic Condition of the Women of Mandai Block with special reference to Central Governments Developmental Schemes Implemented in Tripura

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ABSTRACT:

Tripura being a land locked North East Indian state; its economy mainly depends upon agriculture, horticulture and rubber plantation. Being a developing economy majority of its population depends on Government's welfare scheme for the upliftment and economic survival. Basic necessities like clean fuel for cooking, toilet for dignified life is luxury for these people. Without government help these people are not able to get these facilities. In this paper an attempt made to study the women empowerment through the Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana (PMUY), Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (SBA) and Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojna (PMJDY) scheme. Under these schemes the gas, toilet and bank account were given the women member of the family which transform their life in many ways. The study was confine to Mandai Block of West Tripura District only. Altogether 151 women were selected and interviewed from the three villages. The study confine to socio economic development of the women of Mandai Block of West Tripura.

INTRODUCTION:

Tripura, which was once a princely state was merged with India on 15th October 1949 after signing of the Tripura Merger Agreement on 9th September, 1949 and gradually became full-fledged state on 21st January 1972 under provisions of the North Eastern AR-EAS Act, 1971. According to the 2011 Census, Tripura has 19 sub-tribes among the tribal population with literacy rate of 87.2%; which was 73.20% in 2001 and 60.44% in 1991. Tripura is a land-locked state which shares its boundary with Bangladesh from North, West and South, covering 856 km and the remaining border with Assam and Mizoram covering 53km and 109 km respectively. Being a land locked state; its economy mainly depends upon agriculture, rubber plantation (second largest in India after Kerela), pineapple, oranges, bamboo cultivation. Apart from those, in the year 1976 ONGC found gas in *Baramura*, which was estimated that one lakh cubic meter gas can be extracted every day. Tripura is also rich in a particular material called "*sadabalu*" which is used to prepare general glassware, it was estimated that near *Bishramganj* (close to Agartala) a deposit of about 0.16 million tonne of such materials can be extracted. Moreover, Tripura also produces 750 mega-watts of electricity at Palatana, near Udaipur.

Although rich in natural resources, yet there is poverty & unemployment exists in the state of Tripura. Therefore, the present study focuses on some key aspects to study the socio-economic conditions of Tripura's Tribal population in general and Tribal women in particular.

It is true that the intention behind government policy sounds beneficial but it is the execution and implementation of such policy which makes a government policy great or grave. Irrespective of the kind of policy, whether related to social or economic development, ultimately it should focus on the welfare of the people by eradicating poverty; improve the health facilities, education, safety & security for the women, electricity, water, connectivity, fair prices and so on. The purpose of this paper is to study the socio-economic conditions of Schedule Tribal women of Mandai Block situated in Tripura, one of the tiny states of Northeast India, which in one way or other will reflect, whether implementation of various policies of central government were done effectively or not? This is mainly to examine whether a country can claim to be developed, having regional disparities in various areas.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To study the socio-economic condition of Tribal Women and
2. To study some of the central government policies implementation in Tripura such and its role for empowerment and quality of life of women.

METHODOLOGY:

The study is mainly based on primary data. Data were collected through an interview of the beneficiary of the Central Government schemes. All together 151 women were interviewed and their response were recorded and analyzed. The schemes under the study were (i) Beti Bachao, Beti Pado movement (BBBP) (ii) Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana (PMUY) (iii) Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (SBA) (iv) Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojna (PMJDY).

Hence, a non-probability sampling technique was selected that is based on convenience, characteristics of a population and the objective of the study popularly known as purposive sampling, which was used for the present study to select the three villages of the Mandai Block's namely Ashigarh, Patnipara and Mandainagar. The samples were selected from 151 families' women population of the three villages.

Table 1: Details of Family Sample Survey:

Village	Sample
Ashigarh	25
Patnipara	50
Mandainagar	76
Total	151

Source: Authors Compilation

In the present study primary data are collected through scheduling technique using structured questionnaire. The questionnaires were tested by Cronbach Alpha through SPSS version 25. Cronbach's alpha is a measure of internal consistency, that is, how closely a set of items are related as a group. According to various professionals Cronbach alpha with a score of 0.6 is considered to be the acceptable threshold. In the present study the Cronbach alpha score was 0.64 (refer Table 2).

Table 2: Cronbach alpha score

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
0.640	4

Source: Author's Compilation through SPSS

Secondary data for the study were collected through books, journals, online articles, census 2001 and 2011 report, Report of Directorate of Economics and Statistics of Tripura 2017-18, GOI press release and GOI websites.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

In this present study various literatures were studied to understand the problems regarding socio-economic status of rural tribal women and their probable solution. Socio-economic status includes family income, education, occupation, banking facilities, etc. which are analyzed in relation to one other. One such literature where Ghosh (2008) in his study "Women in Governance in Tripura" advocated that gradually rural women are taking active roles in socio-political issues and does not confine themselves as meek or mute spectator or ornament in decision making process. He added further that most of the rural women who were active member in Panchayat had no previous political exposure or linkage yet they not only raise issues related to exclusively for women but for the whole village and tries to bring solution.

In addition, Meganathan & Arumugam (2012) in their paper "Self Help Groups and Economic Empowerment of Women in Paramakudi" concluded that economic development can be achieved through women empowerment; where self-help group activities play a pivotal role in socio-economic revolution in rural areas by improving economic condition.

However, Singh (2014) in his paper "A study of Socio- Economic Status of Scheduled Caste People of Kangra" reflects that quality education for such rural people is mere dream as most of them depend upon agriculture which does not generate much output. Majority of respondents live in kucha house. Most of them have electricity, water connection and latrine facility. Apart from the agriculture, MGNREGA was the only rural employment programme in the village.

Barman (2014) in his paper "Socio-Economic status of Schedule Caste People in Kamrup District of Assam" found that socio-economic status is low in SC people of Kamrup due to financial glitches. Therefore, such population is far from education, necessary information, motivation and awareness. As a result of which they are unable to take advantages of reservation

policy; which force them to lag behind from the rest of the population. He concluded further that country cannot develop if such population lagged behind. Therefore, development of SC population should not be mere matter of compassion or charity but should be a developmental necessity.

Moreover, according to Iyer, et.al (2013) in their paper “Caste and Entrepreneurship in India” observed that the representations of tribal families in entrepreneurship are very less which means they are more dependent on Agriculture and nature. As a result of which the government rural development programme also play a vital role in supporting the livelihood of rural tribal. Such development programme promotes education, hygiene, earnings, medical facility, housing, ration, etc.

According to Das, et.al (2011) in “Tripura Tribe: A Status Analysis” it is found that there are nine major government rural development programme which plays significant role in Tripura rural tribal population. Such as Total Sanitation Campaign and NREGP (now MGNREGA) were very successful in implementation, the other programme which are supporting some are Swarnajayanti Gram Swaraj Yojana (SGSY), National Old Age Pension Scheme, National Maternity Benefit Scheme, Annapurna, Antodaya, Indira Awas Yojna (IAY) etc. (see table 9).

Hence, the statuses of tribal women are analyzed from the perspective of certain government rural development programmes and its implementation in the rural areas to support and promote the livelihoods rural tribal people. Such rural development programmes which were analyzed in the present study are BBBP, PMUY, SBA and PMJDY.

ANALYSIS:

Beti Bachao, Beti Pado Movement (BBBP)

Education was and is a matter of concern among the tribal community of Tripura in particular. As majority of the tribes of Tripura back in history are “skillful in the art of warfare, rich in culture and proud of their heritage but they were unlettered”. Hence, the movement like ‘Jana shiksha’ among the tribal youths emerges from time to time since its inception through ‘Tripura Rajya Jana Siksha Samiti’ on 27 December, 1945 to end social injustice and superstitions through education. Eventually, the result of such, is quite evidential, that is, awareness about education among the women in Mandai is quite high as all the chosen samples are literate. As per the 2011 census the literacy rate among the female was 82.7% which in due course increased. As per the present study on the three villages it was found that most of the women have completed their secondary and higher secondary (combined) score is 45%; primary education and upper primary education score 28% and 22%; and it is also found that some of them are even graduate and post graduate (refer Table 3). The higher rate of literate women in tribal community bring radical changes by not only improving their family but also improves society and economy as a whole and also the next generation.

Table 3: Qualification of Women

Qualification	Frequency	Percent
Primary Schooling (Class1 to 5)	43	28%
Upper Primary Schooling (Class6 to 8)	33	22%
Secondary & Higher Secondary	67	45%
Graduate& Post Graduate	8	5%
Total	151	100%

Source: Authors Compilation

According to the 2001 Census the literacy rate among the tribes were very poor as 50% of Tripuri females are literate, which is one of the major tribal populations. 'Tripura' & 'Debbarma' are the major tribal population of Tripura state, since 2001. It is indeed a long way to cover and now, it can be seen that all the samples of the present study are literate and even some of them are graduate and post graduate. Due to education many of them started their own small business, many of them work as a teacher and helpers in Anganwadi, and some of them are working as nurses and helpers in hospitals, which reflects education can bring not only bring positive change in the life but also in upcoming generations as well.

Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana (PMUY):

PMUY is one of the flagship movements of Central Government which was launched by Hon'ble Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi on 1st of May, 2016 in Ballia, Uttar Pradesh. At that time, it was projected that this scheme will provide 5 crore LPG connection to the families living below poverty line. In addition, a supporting amount of Rs.1600 per connection will be provided in upcoming 3 years. This yojna ensures women's empowerment and safeguard them from chronic disease which occurs due to inhaling smoke during cooking by burning firewood, especially in rural India. Undoubtedly, the yojna was excellent program but controversies emerged with regards to the refilling of the cylinders.

Although the present study does not enquire about refilling of cylinders but, it has been observed that tribal women of Mandai Block use LPG (Liquid Petroleum Gas) as their cooking fuel over the fire wood. The most popular picture among the tribal communities is that they depend on fire wood from the nearby jungles to cook their food. On the contrary the tribal community of Mandai under the study depends on LPG for their cooking. The two vital reasons are, firstly the awareness about PMUY (Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana) in the rural areas and secondly being Mandai Block is under west district and close to Agartala (capital of Tripura) hence connectivity and reach become convenient and regular for LPG cylinders delivery. It is not that all are using LPG some of them are still depends on firewood.

Table 4: Use of Cooking Fuel

Fuel	Frequency	Percentage
LPG	149	99%
Firewood	2	1%
	151	100%

Source: Authors Compilation

Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (SBA):

In one of the speeches addressing the joint session of the Parliament Hon'ble President Shri Ram Nath Kovind, mentioned that due to lack of toilets in the rural areas, crores of people were forced, to have an unhealthy and an undignified life, particularly “daughters and daughters-in-law”. He also added that it is due to construction of so many toilets in recent past, numerous poor people's life have been spared from various kind of diseases and more than three lakh lives have been saved, Kovind said. (Economic Times, January 31, 2019). As per the Economic Survey presented by Hon'ble Union Minister for Finance and Corporate Affairs, Smt. Nirmala Sitharaman, Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) one of the largest cleanliness drive through which, 99.2 per cent of rural India has been covered in the last four years. Since October 2014, over 9.5 crore toilets have been built all over the country and 564,658 villages have been declared Open Defecation Free (ODF). As on 14 June 2019, 30 States/UTs are 100 per cent covered with Individual household Latrine (IHHL). SBM has significantly improved health outcomes; which reduces diarrhea and malaria among children below five years, still-birth and low birth weight (new born with weight less than 2.5kgs). (PIB-GOI, July 2019).

According to the Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation, some of India's largest states, namely Gujarat, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh, have managed to declare their rural areas as Open Defecation Free (ODF). The survey also reveals that once Indian peoples are amongst the highest number in the world defecating in the open, but since 2014 defecating in open came down to 25 crore from 53 crore, over 4.5 lakh villages and 453 districts have also become ODF, consisting of sixteen states, which shows improvement in rural areas due to the mission (NDTV August 8 2019).

The states and UTs which have been declared ODF are Gujarat, Andaman and Nicobar Islands, Daman and Diu, Andhra Pradesh, Chandigarh, Arunachal Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Karnataka, Dadra and Nagar Haveli, Haryana, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Rajasthan, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir, Jharkhand, Kerala, Lakshadweep, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Puducherry, Punjab, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand.

Although Tripura is not in the above list, but all the samples in this study use IHHL for their morning defecation in their houses (refer Table 5). The couple of reasons are: mass scale campaign and successful implementation, secondly awareness about sanitation and hygiene among the women of Mandai Block.

Table 4: Use of IHHL

Sanitation Facility	Frequency	Percentage
IHHL	151	100%
Total	151	100%

Source: Authors Compilation

Pradhan Mantri Jan DhanYojna (PMJDY):

Financial Inclusion has been the buzzing word in the contemporary period, where central governments keep no stone unturned and started another landmark scheme in August 2014 – ‘Pradhan Mantri Jan DhanYojna’. Under this scheme original target was 7.5 crore bank accounts to be open for those who do not have any bank account. In other words, they are the ones who are not connected with main stream of finance. As on 31st January 2015, banks already opened 12.54 crore accounts. Today coverage of almost 100% has been achieved. All the eight districts of Tripura have successfully covered the set target (refer table 5). (GOI, 2019).

Table 5: District wise House Hold Report

District Name	Allotted Wards-SSAs	Wards-SSAs SurveyDone	Household Coverage (%)
Dhalai	80	80	100.00%
Gomati	80	80	100.00%
Khowai	88	88	100.00%
North Tripura	102	102	100.00%
Sepahijala	106	106	100.00%
South Tripura	112	112	100.00%
Unakoti	61	61	100.00%
West Tripura	138	138	100.00%

Source: <https://pmjdy.gov.in/statewise-statistics>

Therefore, in the present study even when the question was asked regarding the bank account, except three of them all the samples of the present study have bank accounts in their names (refer table 6). It is also evidential from the GOI report that only 51% of the total accounts opened are in the names of females.

Table 6: Women having Bank Account

Bank Account	Frequency	Percentage
Having Bank Account	148	98%
Not Having Bank Account	3	2%
Total	151	100%

Source: Authors Compilation

Another fact of not having bank account yet, is the traditional practice, that is, earning member will have the bank account. In the present study all the three females who don't have the bank accounts by their names as because of two prominent reasons, those are: all the three females are housewives and not the earning members – as they depend on their husbands income, hence husband has bank account but not the females. Moreover their education qualification is up to class eight which might also be another reason for not having bank account – as they are not aware or shy off.

The remaining 148 females have their bank account by their names where majority of them are working as Anganwadi Teacher or worker, Helper in schools and Hospitals, having their own business. It is also quite interesting to know that many of the housewives have their bank account as all of them are passed either secondary or higher secondary or graduation. Hence, we can conclude that education leads to awareness and awareness leads to financially include in main stream of finance.

Observation:

Some of the observations made on the basis of correlation are as follows (refer table 7):

Table 7: Correlation with some variables

Sl. No	Correlation	Value
1	Qualification vs Bank	0.47905015
2	Income vs Bank	0.31025106
3	Qualification vs Income	0.28214945
4	Income vs Fuel	-0.04784141

Source: Authors Compilation

1. Qualification and having bank account have a positively correlation (score 0.48), which signifies that education brings awareness and awareness leads to the development of society and economy.
2. It is also evidential from the above score that income is positively correlated with having bank account, as it reflects the fact that PMJDY campaign was seriously implemented by making people aware and by winning their trust and bring them into the main stream of finance of the economy.
3. It is also quite interesting to note that qualification and income are positively correlated as it completes the cycle that it is education that can eradicate poverty and has the power to generate income. Although correlation is only 0.28, yet it is a positive sign.
4. Most interesting to note, is that, as income rises – standard of living also rises, or in other words one moves towards making their lives easy. For example, as income rises one will tend to move from fire wood to LPG/PNG. Paradoxically here there is negative relation between income and cooking fuel which means irrespective of income of the female member PMUY works.

CONCLUSION:

In this present study, it can be concluded that education among the tribal women has improved and is improving, as the study reflects that 45% of the samples has passed secondary and higher secondary exams as a result of which many of them started their own business, became teacher and helper in Anganwadi, nurse and helper in the Hospitals and so on. Such educational awareness brings consciousness regarding earnings and savings, use of LPG as cooking fuel. The other side reflects that still 50% (combining primary 28% and upper primary 22%) of the tribal

women find it difficult to pass class 8 (refer table:3). In this present study focus was mainly on female education and not on saving “female fetus” therefore that implementation of ‘BetiPadao’ movement is yet to reach its goal.

Moreover, the movement to bring the tribal and rural people in the main stream of finance through ‘Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojna’ was a great success in the way of implementation as under this scheme original target was 7.5 crore bank accounts to be opened for those who do not have any bank account; in other words, who are not connected with main stream of finance, as on 31st January 2015, banks already opened 12.54 crore accounts. Today a coverage of almost 100% has been achieved. The present study also reflects that almost 100% (i.e., 98%) of the tribal women has bank account and they are using it.

Another central government policy Pradhan Mantri Ujjala Yojana under which rural women uses LPG instead of firewood, as per the GOI the programme provides the rural women an opportunity to get rid of smoke while cooking with firewood, dry cow dung, and dry leaves. Although the present study does not enquire about the refill of cylinder from the families but according to Gopal Krishan Gupta, Joint Secretary, Ministry of New & Renewable Energy once said “It has been realized that poor people are not able to refill the LPG cylinder given to them under the scheme. Thus, the Centre is planning to bring a new scheme for power cooking with solar”.

The most successful movement of the central government is ‘Swachh Bharat Abhiyan’, where many states are declared by the government as 100% Open Defecation Free (ODF) but Tripura is not amongst those states yet all the samples in this present study use IHHL for their morning defecation in their houses (refer Table 5). The couple of reasons for success of SBM are: mass scale campaign and successful implementation, secondly awareness about sanitation and hygiene among the women of Mandai Block. As on 14 June 2019, 30 States/UTs are 100 per cent covered with Individual household Latrine (IHHL). SBM has significantly improved health outcomes; which reduces diarrhea and malaria among children below five years, still-birth and low birth weight (new born with weight less than 2.5kgs). Therefore, it can also be concluded that the socio-economic condition of the tribal women of Mandai Block is quite standard.

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